

ISSUES OF INNOVATIVE INVESTMENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC INTEGRATION

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Abstract. *The relevance of the chosen topic is determined by the need to study the mechanisms contributing to increasing the investment attractiveness of Uzbekistan in the field of innovation, as well as assessing the challenges and opportunities arising in the process of international economic integration. In the context of global competition and digital transformation, measures to improve the investment climate, protect intellectual property, and develop the country's scientific and educational potential are of particular importance.*

Keywords: *innovative platforms, digital technologies, digital Uzbekistan, robotics, artificial intelligence, global economy, international economic INTEGRATION.*

INTRODUCTION

International economic integration is the process of developing sustainable relationships between individual countries or groups of countries, which can lead to a gradual merger of national economic systems. This process is closely related and based on the internationalization of the economy, which also represents the expansion of the reproductive process beyond the national economy. International economic integration plays an important role in the modern world, helping to make more rational use of raw materials, fuel and labor resources, improving interregional relations. The beginning of the XXI century. It was characterized by an increased search for new opportunities to develop the production of innovative products, which in the modern world economy seems to be the most appropriate way to bring the economy or certain types of production to higher technological levels. The innovative development path is determined by the inevitability of using three components: large investments, special competencies, and a relatively long period of time. Expert communities have come to the conclusion about the growing role of innovative investments and international investment cooperation in the global economy. The instability of the global economy has left a serious negative imprint on this process.

Historically, interest in innovation in the economy originated during the industrial revolution, when industries such as mechanical engineering, the chemical industry, and the textile industry gained significant development, which significantly accelerated economic growth and allowed developing countries to enter the global market. Since the middle of the 20th century, with the development of information technology, innovation has begun to play an even more important role, becoming the basis for the growth of countries such as the United States, Japan, Germany and other world leaders. A trade organization, the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, which has helped attract investment in various industries, including innovative ones. However, in the 21st century, the integration of world economies has entered a new phase related to digitalization, global environmental challenges and the development of new

technologies. The development of sectors such as information technology, biotechnology, renewable energy, and artificial intelligence has become one of the most significant drivers of economic growth in advanced economies. This has led to the need to create new institutional frameworks for investment regulation and intellectual property protection, as well as to develop new strategies for managing global economic processes. In recent decades, special attention has been paid to the role of international economic associations in stimulating innovation processes and investments. In the face of global competition and an ever-changing technological landscape, countries are striving to create conditions for effective integration into international innovation chains by strengthening cross-border cooperation and seeking to harmonize regulations and legal acts related to innovation.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

For the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is at the stage of active economic reforms and deepening cooperation with international and regional integration associations, attracting and effectively using innovative investments is of strategic importance. Uzbekistan is strengthening ties with its CIS partners, striving for closer cooperation with the EAEU and other international organizations, while forming its own model of innovative development focused on openness, technological renewal and entrepreneurship support. In early April 2025, an important international summit was held in Samarkand — the meeting of the European Union with the countries of Central Asia. This was the first summit in this format, and it immediately received serious attention, both from the participants and in the international arena. It brought together the heads of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan, as well as top EU representatives Antonio Costa and Ursula von der Leyen.

The main topic of the summit was the expansion of cooperation in various fields, from economics to security. There was a lot of talk about trade, investment, and infrastructure. The Europeans are interested in working more actively with Central Asia, including supporting the development of transport routes such as the so-called "Middle Route", which connects China with Europe bypassing Russia. This area is especially relevant now, and Samarkand has become a platform where it has already been discussed at the highest level.

Energy was also in the spotlight. The parties discussed the transition to "green" energy, the development of renewable sources — solar and wind power plants. The EU is ready to support such projects financially and technologically. At the same time, the topic of energy security and the need to diversify supplies was raised.

A separate section was devoted to digitalization. The EU is interested in Central Asia developing as a technologically modern region. It was about digital infrastructure, cybersecurity and the introduction of electronic public services. The topics of education and science were also touched upon — the parties plan to strengthen student exchange and support research initiatives.

Security issues were also not ignored. Especially in light of the situation in Afghanistan, which continues to have an impact on the whole of Central Asia. We discussed the joint fight against terrorism, extremism, as well as the problem of drug trafficking. The EU expressed its willingness to cooperate in these areas and share its experience.

And, of course, humanitarian issues such as culture, education, and tourism were not left out. They also see great potential in this: mutual exchanges, joint projects, festivals, interuniversity partnership programs.

The Samarkand Summit showed that Europe's interest in Central Asia is only growing. The region has become an important partner, and both sides are committed to long-term and strategic cooperation. By the way, Samarkand is increasingly strengthening its position as the

diplomatic capital of the region — the city is becoming a platform for important international dialogues.

The EU—Central Asia Summit, held in Samarkand in April 2025, was a prime example of how innovative investments can form the basis for strengthening international economic integration. In the face of global challenges and changing geopolitical realities, the Central Asian countries and the European Union are actively discussing areas for mutually beneficial cooperation, including the development of innovative technologies, infrastructure and green energy.

One of the central topics of the summit was attracting investments in digitalization and sustainable development. The European Union has shown its willingness to support projects related to infrastructure modernization, the development of renewable energy sources and digital technologies, which are key aspects for the further economic integration of Central Asia into the global economy. The importance of innovative initiatives such as the construction of new transport corridors and the introduction of energy technologies demonstrates the desire of the countries of the region and the EU for closer cooperation based on mutual investments in the development of modern industries.

The Samarkand Summit highlighted the importance of innovative investments as a key element of integration into the international economy, providing new opportunities for growth and sustainable development of Central Asian countries in the context of global economic and technological transformations. Several key steps need to be taken to successfully implement innovative investments and strengthen the international economic integration of Central Asia with the European Union. First of all, it is important to create a favorable investment climate. This requires the development of a stable legal framework that will ensure the protection of investors' rights and interests. It is necessary to simplify the processes of business registration, obtaining building permits, and supporting public-private partnerships for joint projects.

Another important aspect is the development of infrastructure and innovative ecosystems. Central Asia needs to modernize its transport and energy systems, as well as create innovative hubs and technology parks that will support startups and developing technologies. Improving educational and scientific initiatives, including the creation of joint research centers and incubators for startups, is also becoming an important element.

Central Asia should actively move towards sustainable development, especially in the energy sector. This will require support for renewable energy sources through government programs, tax incentives, and subsidies for companies that will invest in green technologies. It is also necessary to modernize the energy infrastructure in order to increase its efficiency and environmental friendliness.

The development of the digital economy is another important element of integration. In order to become an attractive region for innovative investments, Central Asia needs to actively introduce digital technologies into the economy. This includes creating platforms for e-commerce and government services, improving cybersecurity, and developing digital literacy.

Thus, the successful integration of Central Asia into the international economy through innovative investments requires an integrated approach, including reforms in the fields of legislation, infrastructure, education and technology.

CONCLUSION

The study of innovative investments in the context of international economic integration revealed that innovative investments are a key factor for achieving sustainable economic growth

and increasing the competitiveness of countries in the context of globalization. The most important elements of an effective investment strategy are to support scientific and technological progress, create a favorable climate for cross-border investments and protect intellectual property. Special attention is paid to the role of international economic associations such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), the European Union and others in stimulating innovation processes and attracting investments. The example of the recent Samarkand summit showed how an important element of international integration is the development of cooperation in the field of high technologies and innovations, as well as the creation of joint platforms for sustainable and mutually beneficial investments. The projected future of innovative investments is linked to the need for countries to adapt to rapidly changing global challenges such as digitalization, environmental change, and the development of new technologies. It is important that national Governments continue to implement innovative strategies and create conditions for further engagement in international cooperation.

Thus, innovative investments play a strategically important role in the process of economic integration and global development, creating new opportunities for countries and regions that contribute to their progress on the world stage.

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